

Integration of Image Segmentation with L_2 Optimization Theories of Statistics

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Abstract

Minimum distance estimation methodology based on an empirical distribution function has been popular due to its desirable properties. Even though the statistical literature is awash with research on the minimum distance estimation, most of it is confined to the theoretical aspects: only a few statisticians conducted research on the application of the method to real-world problems. Through this paper, we extend the domain of application of this methodology to various fields by providing a solution to a rather challenging and complicated computational problem. The problem this paper tackles is image segmentation that has been widely used in medical sciences. We propose a novel method based on the classical minimum distance estimation theory to solve the image segmentation problem. We demonstrate that the proposed method successfully solves the segmentation problem when it is applied to magnetic resonance images.

Key Words: Cramer-von Mises, empirical distribution, magnetic resonance, minimum distance, netgain, statistical noise

1. Introduction

The minimum distance (MD) estimation method is a nonparametric technique that minimizes a “distance” to obtain estimators for statistical models. The distance used in the method is a difference between an assumed function from models – e.g., distribution function – and one from a sample of observations such as the empirical distribution function. There is a vast body of literature that illustrates the desirable properties of the MD estimators such as consistency, asymptotic normality, and robustness: see, e.g., Donoho (1988), Koul (1970, 1985, 1986), and Parr (1979). The MD estimation gained our attention since it can be adapted to solve various statistical estimation problems in that the method with different distance functions and integrating measures provides efficient and robust estimators. For a linear regression model, Koul (2002) proved that the MD estimators obtained from a Cramer-von Mises (CvM) type distance function with Lebesgue and degenerate integrating measures are the most efficient when errors in the model are independent normal and logistic random variables. By using an influence function, Parr (1979) empirically verified that the MD method with the CvM-type distance provides the most robust estimators when the sample of independent observations is contaminated, which implies it contains extreme outliers. Kim (2020) proved that the method can also be applied to a linear regression model with dependent errors and empirically demonstrated that it is more efficient than other well-celebrated estimators such as Huber, Tukey, and maximum likelihood estimators. The past research, thus, motivate us to employ the MD estimation equipped with the CvM-type distance function in this study that tackles the image segmentation problem.

One caveat against using the MD estimation method for solving the proposed image segmentation problem is its computational complexity, which is illustrated in the next section. An important

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point to bear in mind is that a naive application of existing numerical optimization methods to minimize the CvM-type distance – which is generally expressed as an integrated square difference of weighted residual empirical processes – will lead to a slow and potentially incorrect computation. Rather than resorting to them, we, therefore, thoroughly investigate the structure of the CvM-type distance function and exploit some of its useful characteristics to expedite the computation. To that end, we propose a novel algorithm to enable the application of the MD method to the image segmentation problem for the first time. The code used in this paper is available in the GitHub repository: https://github.com/jwboys26/Segmenting_Together.

2. Minimum distance estimator

This section will define the image segmentation problem and discuss the application of the MD method to the segmentation. To that end, we introduce a statistical model with unknown parameters and fit it to the image. For the model fitting, we will seek MD estimators of the underlying parameters in the model through the CvM-type L_2 distance function and propose a fast computational algorithm to obtain those estimators. To be more precise, we begin with some definitions and a model for the image segmentation.

Definition 2.1. In digital imaging, a **pixel** is a physical point in a raster image. A collection of MN pixels is denoted by

$$S = \{(i, j) : 1 \leq i \leq M, 1 \leq j \leq N\},$$

where M and N are known positive integers.

An image, Img , is a map from S to the real line \mathbb{R} that is expressed as an $M \times N$ matrix

$$Img := \begin{bmatrix} g(1,1) & g(1,2) & \cdots & g(1,N) \\ g(2,1) & \cdots & \cdots & g(2,N) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ g(M,1) & \cdots & \cdots & g(M,N) \end{bmatrix},$$

where $g : \mathbb{N}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^D$ and $g(i, j)$ denotes the value of the image at the (i, j) th pixel. Clearly, $Img = g(S)$. Here, D denotes the number of channels. If $D = 1$, the resultant output is a grayscale image, while a color image that we commonly see corresponds to $D = 3$. This study considers grayscale images, i.e., $D = 1$. Pixel values of the grayscale images represent the contrast that ranges from the darkest (black) to the brightest (white).

Let K be a positive integer and S_k , $1 \leq k \leq K$ denote a partition of S so that $S_i \cap S_j = \emptyset$ for $i \neq j$ and

$$S = \bigcup_{k=1}^K S_k.$$

Accordingly, let n_k and n denote cardinalities of S_k and S , respectively so that $n = \sum_{k=1}^K n_k = MN$. Subsequently, we write

$$S_k = \{(x_{ik}, y_{ik}) \in \mathbb{N}^2, i = 1, 2, \dots, n_k : 1 \leq x_{ik} \leq M, 1 \leq y_{ik} \leq N\},$$

so that the image can be segmented into K sub-images: $g(S_1), g(S_2), \dots, g(S_K)$. For $1 \leq i \leq n_k$ and $k = 1, \dots, K$, let $S_1^\dagger, S_2^\dagger, \dots, S_K^\dagger$ be a set of a mutually exclusive partition of S by K different colors and

$$g(x_{ik}, y_{ik}) = p_k \quad \text{if } (x_{ik}, y_{ik}) \in S_k^\dagger,$$

where $0 \leq p_k \leq 1$; black and white pixels take a value of 0 and 1, respectively, while a gray pixel takes an intermediate value.

Example 2.1. Consider $K = 2$ and refer to Figure 1. In the left panel of the figure, let S_1^\dagger and S_2^\dagger denote collections of white and black pixels, respectively. Note that a pair of S_1^\dagger and S_2^\dagger is a mutually

exclusive, exhaustive partition of S where S is the collection of all pixels in the entire rectangle. Hence, for any pixel $s \in S$,

$$g(s) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } s \in S_1^\dagger; \\ 0, & \text{if } s \in S_2^\dagger. \end{cases}$$

In this example, p_1 and p_2 corresponding to S_1^\dagger and S_2^\dagger will be 1 and 0, respectively.

For $1 \leq i \leq n_k$ and $k = 1, \dots, K$, define $\tilde{g} : \mathbb{N}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by the following relation

$$\tilde{g}(x_{ik}, y_{ik}) := g(x_{ik}, y_{ik}) + \varepsilon_i, \quad (1)$$

where ε_i are some random variables. In the literature, ε_i is called “noise” since it blurs the true pixel value $g(x_{ik}, y_{ik})$. In the presence of noise, we will observe $\tilde{g}(s)$ for $s \in S$, instead of $g(s)$: the right panel of Figure 1 illustrates the presence of noise.

When no noise is observed as shown in the left panel of Figure 1, separating white pixels from black pixels (or vice versa), i.e., identifying S_1^\dagger and S_2^\dagger does not foment any problems. In the right panel of Figure 1, the same segmentation task – separating the originally-white pixels from other pixels – is encumbered by the presence of noise. Thus, the noise renders the segmentation task more challenging and error-prone: Figures 2-5 illustrate the results of the segmentation deteriorate even more as stronger noise is introduced to original images. For general K , the same conclusion holds. Therefore, the successful image segmentation hinges upon how to closely identify $S_1^\dagger, S_2^\dagger, \dots, S_K^\dagger$ when they are blurred by noise, i.e., $\tilde{g}(S)$ is observed instead of $g(S)$ due to the presence of the noise. In the sequel, let $s_{ik} := (x_{ik}, y_{ik})$ denote the i th pixel of S_k .

Figure 1: Images with and without noise.

Next, we shall define the distance function. Let

$$\mathcal{S}^K = \{(S_1, S_2, \dots, S_K) : \cup_{i=1}^K S_i = S, S_i \cap S_j = \emptyset, \text{ for all } i \neq j\}.$$

Note that any $S \in \mathcal{S}^K$ will be then a K -tuple – whose components are collections of pixels – and partition S into K exhaustive, exclusive sets of pixels. Accordingly, define

$$\mathcal{L}(S) = \int \sum_{k=1}^K \left[\frac{1}{n} \sum_{s_i \in S_k} \left\{ \mathbf{I}(\tilde{g}(s_i) - p_k \leq x) - \mathbf{I}(-\tilde{g}(s_i) + p_k < x) \right\} \right]^2 dH(x),$$

for any $S = (S_1, \dots, S_K) \in \mathcal{S}^K$, where $\mathbf{I}(\cdot)$ is an indicator function, and $H : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a nondecreasing right continuous function having left limits. The above class of distances, one for each H , is deduced from Koul (2002) which deals with parametric linear and nonlinear regression and autoregressive models. The image segmentation problem in terms of the above distance is equivalent to solving the minimization problem

$$\hat{S} = \operatorname{argmin}_{S \in \mathcal{S}^K} \mathcal{L}(S),$$

where $\hat{S} = (\hat{S}_1, \dots, \hat{S}_K)$. Before proceeding further, we need the following assumptions on ε_i : ε_i 's are independently and identically distributed according to F with a finite second moment where F is continuous and symmetric around zero, i.e., $F(-x) = 1 - F(x)$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$. We do not, however, assume knowledge of this distribution.

Consider the segmentation problem of the black and white image, that is, $S = S_1 \cup S_2$ and $S_1 \cap S_2 = \emptyset$. Then the MD estimator (\hat{S}_1, \hat{S}_2) can be defined as

$$\mathcal{L}(\hat{S}_1, \hat{S}_2) = \inf_{(S_1, S_2) \in \mathcal{S}^2} \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2). \quad (2)$$

In general, a solution to the optimization problem in (2) does not have any closed-form expressions, and hence, we seek a solution through numerical optimization. To that end, we start with a pair of collections of randomly selected pixels $(S_1^{(0)}, S_2^{(0)})$ in the initial stage, find a better pair of collections $(S_1^{(1)}, S_2^{(1)})$ that yields a smaller value of \mathcal{L} than the value at the previous stage, and keep iterating this procedure until the convergence. Then, how can we select a better pair of collections? To answer this question, we introduce a concept of a “netgain” that is the quintessential part of our proposed method. For some pixel $s \in S_i$, let $S_i^{(-\{s\})}$ and $S_i^{(+\{s\})}$ denote $S_i \setminus \{s\}$ and $S_i \cup \{s\}$, respectively.

Definition 2.2. Consider a pixel $s_i \in S_1$. Then a netgain of s_i is defined as

$$NG(s_i; S_1) := \mathcal{L}(S_1^{(-\{s_i\})}, S_2^{(+\{s_i\})}) - \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2),$$

which is a difference between two distance functions before and after transferring s_i from S_1 to S_2 . Similarly, a netgain of $s_j \in S_2$ is defined as

$$NG(s_j; S_2) := \mathcal{L}(S_1^{(+\{s_j\})}, S_2^{(-\{s_j\})}) - \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2).$$

Consider $s_k \in S_i$. Recall that $S_i^{(-\{s_k\})}$ and $S_j^{(+\{s_k\})}$ are $S_i \setminus \{s_k\}$ and $S_j \cup \{s_k\}$, respectively. For the sake of brevity, let $S_i^{(-k)}$ and $S_j^{(+k)}$ denote these two sets, respectively. Analogously, for $s_k, s_h \in S_i$, let $S_i^{(-k,h)}$ and $S_j^{(+k,h)}$ denote $S_i \setminus \{s_k, s_h\}$ and $S_j \cup \{s_k, s_h\}$, respectively. Adoption of the concept of the netgain makes it convenient to analyze the distance function in that any difference between distance functions – one obtained from the original (S_1, S_2) and another obtained after the transfer of several pixels from S_1 to S_2 – can be written as the sum of netgains of those pixels. For example, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(S_1^{(-k,h)}, S_2^{(+k,h)}) - \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2) &= NG(s_k; S_1) + NG(s_h; S_1^{(-k)}), \\ &= NG(s_h; S_1) + NG(s_k; S_1^{(-h)}), \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

for $s_k, s_h \in S_1$. Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(S_1^{(+k,h)}, S_2^{(-k,h)}) - \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2) &= NG(s_k; S_2) + NG(s_h; S_2^{(-k)}), \\ &= NG(s_h; S_2) + NG(s_k; S_2^{(-h)}), \end{aligned}$$

when $s_k, s_h \in S_2$. For the general case, consider any $S_1^{sub} \subset S_1$ where $S_1^{sub} = S_1 \setminus \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_L\}$. The difference of the distance functions before and after the transfer of these L pixels from S_1 to S_2 can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{L}(S_1^{sub}, S_1^{sub}) - \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2) = NG(u_1; S_1) + \sum_{i=2}^L NG(u_i; S_1 \setminus \cup_{j=1}^{i-1} \{u_j\}).$$

For further discussion, define two sets:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{NG}(S_1) &:= \{s_i \in S_1 : NG(s_i; S_1) < 0\}, \\ \mathcal{NG}(S_2) &:= \{s_j \in S_2 : NG(s_j; S_2) < 0\}. \end{aligned}$$

From the definition of the netgain, $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$ is a set of pixels which originally belong to S_1 , and whose relocation from S_1 to S_2 will decrease the distance function. Similarly, $\mathcal{NG}(S_2)$ is a set of pixels whose relocation in the opposite way will decrease the distance function.

At this juncture, one important question arises: which pixels of S_1 and S_2 should be relocated to each other in order to decrease the distance function? It is not unreasonable to consider pixels that belong to $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$ and $\mathcal{NG}(S_2)$ as potential candidates. For the convenience of further analysis, let $\mathcal{NG}(S_1) = \{s_1^1, s_2^1, \dots, s_{m_1}^1\}$ and $\mathcal{NG}(S_2) = \{s_1^2, s_2^2, \dots, s_{m_2}^2\}$. Transferring all elements of $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$ from S_1 to S_2 will result in two new sets: $S_1 \setminus \mathcal{NG}(S_1)$ and $S_2 \cup \mathcal{NG}(S_1)$. Then, the difference between the consequential and initial distance functions can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}(S_1 \setminus \mathcal{NG}(S_1), S_2 \cup \mathcal{NG}(S_1)) - \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2) = NG(s_1^1; S_1) + \sum_{i=2}^{m_1} NG(s_i^1; S_1 \setminus \cup_{j=1}^{i-1} \{s_j^1\}).$$

It is worth noting the following facts; (1) $s_1^1 \in \mathcal{NG}(S_1)$ implies that the first term in the right-hand side of the above equation is less than 0, which means the transfer of s_1^1 will always decrease the distance function; (2) the summand of the right-hand side of the equation $NG(s_i^1; S_1 \setminus \cup_{j=1}^{i-1} \{s_j^1\})$ is not always negative even though $NG(s_i^1; S_1) < 0$; and (3) transfer of all s_i^1 in $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$, hence, does not guarantee the greatest decrease in the distance function. To accomplish the desired result, define $\mathcal{T}(S_1) = \{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_{m_1^*}\} \subset \mathcal{NG}(S_1)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
t_1 &:= \operatorname{argmin}_{s \in \mathcal{NG}(S_1)} NG(s; S_1), \\
t_2 &:= \operatorname{argmin}_{s \in \mathcal{NG}(S_1)} NG(s; S_1 \setminus \{t_1\}) \text{ subject to } NG(s; S_1 \setminus \{t_1\}) < 0, \\
&\vdots \\
t_{m_1^*} &:= \operatorname{argmin}_{s \in \mathcal{NG}(S_1)} NG(s; S_1 \setminus \cup_{j=1}^{m_1^*-1} \{t_j\}) \\
&\text{subject to } NG(s; S_1 \setminus \cup_{j=1}^{m_1^*-1} \{t_j\}) < 0.
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

To be more precise, we construct $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$ as follows. Among pixels of $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$, find one which has the smallest netgain $NG(s; S_1)$; this pixel will be the first element of $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$, denoted by t_1 . Note that $NG(t_1; S_1) < 0$ by the definition of $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$. Next, among the remaining pixels after removing t_1 from $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$, find t_2 which has the smallest $NG(s; S_1 \setminus \{t_1\})$, and check the sign of the resulting netgain that will play a role of a stopping criterion. If $NG(t_2; S_1 \setminus \{t_1\}) \geq 0$, the construction of $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$ will be halted; otherwise, we add it to $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$ and proceed to find t_3 . Repeating this procedure until the stopping criterion is met will yield $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$. As a result, $m_1^* \leq m_1$. $\mathcal{T}(S_2) \subset \mathcal{NG}(S_2)$ can be obtained in the same manner. By construction, we always have $\mathcal{L}(S_1 / \mathcal{T}(S_1), S_2 \cup \mathcal{T}(S_1)) < \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2)$ and $\mathcal{L}(S_1 \cup \mathcal{T}(S_2), S_2 \setminus \mathcal{T}(S_2)) < \mathcal{L}(S_1, S_2)$. At the moment of trading some elements between S_1 and S_2 , we will, therefore, refer to $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$ and $\mathcal{T}(S_2)$ instead of $\mathcal{NG}(S_1)$ and $\mathcal{NG}(S_2)$.

Starting with an initial pair of sets (S_1, S_2) , we compute $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$ and transfer its elements to S_2 ; let $\tilde{S}_1 = S_1 \setminus \mathcal{T}(S_1)$ and $\tilde{S}_2 = S_2 \cup \mathcal{T}(S_1)$. Now we compute $\mathcal{T}(\tilde{S}_2)$, i.e., we find $s \in \tilde{S}_2$ whose netgain is less than 0 and the transfer of which to \tilde{S}_1 will decrease the distance function. When checking pixels belonging to \tilde{S}_2 , we may need to check the pixels initially belonging to S_2 only, which seems quite reasonable. To put it another way, any elements of $\mathcal{T}(S_1)$ may not be relocated back to S_1 once they move to S_2 .

Table 1: The summary of the proposed algorithm.

Choose a random initial pair (S_1, S_2)
Set $\mathcal{T}_1 = \mathcal{T}_2 = \emptyset$
while $\mathcal{T}_1 \neq \emptyset$ or $\mathcal{T}_2 \neq \emptyset$
compute $\mathcal{T}_1 := \mathcal{T}(S_1)$ and $\mathcal{T}_2 := \mathcal{T}(S_2)$.
transfer all pixels of \mathcal{T}_1 from S_1 to S_2 .
transfer all pixels of \mathcal{T}_2 from S_2 to S_1 .
update S_1 and S_2 to $(S_1 \setminus \mathcal{T}_1) \cup \mathcal{T}_2$ and $(S_2 \setminus \mathcal{T}_2) \cup \mathcal{T}_1$, respectively
end while
Return S_1 and S_2

We examine elements originally belonging to S_2 only when constructing $\mathcal{T}(\tilde{S}_2)$, which implies $\mathcal{T}(\tilde{S}_2) = \mathcal{T}(S_2)$; next, we transfer all pixels of $\mathcal{T}(S_2)$ from \tilde{S}_2 to \tilde{S}_1 . Finally, we have $(S_1 \setminus \mathcal{T}(S_1)) \cup \mathcal{T}(S_2)$ and $(S_2 \cup \mathcal{T}(S_1)) \setminus \mathcal{T}(S_2)$ at the end of the stage; update S_1 and S_2 with these two sets for the next stage. Then we repeat this procedure until we get $\mathcal{T}(S_1) = \mathcal{T}(S_2) = \emptyset$, i.e., there is no need to relocate elements between S_1 and S_2 to decrease the distance function. The proposed algorithm is summarized in Table 1.

3. Simulation studies

3.1 General setup

Recall the model (1). Through this section, we use a collection of pixels

$$S = \{(i, j) : 1 \leq i \leq 200, 1 \leq j \leq 200\},$$

i.e., S is a 200×200 square. As in Example 2.1, we consider $K = 2$ and assume that $g : \mathbb{R}^2 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ takes $p_1 = 1$ and $p_2 = 0$ over S_1^\dagger and S_2^\dagger , respectively. For the error (or noise) of the model in (1), we assume that it follows a normal distribution with a mean of zero and a standard deviation of σ . Kim (2018, 2020) demonstrated that the MD estimators of linear models with both independent and dependent errors – which follow a wide range of distributions, including a normal, logistic, Cauchy, and mixture of two distributions – perform well and compare favorably with well-celebrated estimators. Similar to the findings in Kim (2018, 2020), the MD estimators of this study show similar performance regardless of distributions of the error, and hence, we report the simulation result corresponding to the normal error only. When generating the normal error, we try $\sigma = 0.1, 0.5, \text{ and } 0.8$ for the comparison purpose: the corresponding errors are referred to as mild, moderate, and severe errors, respectively.

The size of all images used for the simulation studies is 200×200 . A segmentation task for a simulated 200×200 image – e.g., the segmentation of the white circle as in Example 2.1 – is not computationally expensive in that it does not take much time. However, some other real images – e.g., medical images – of a large dimension will take a substantial amount of time. Therefore, it is absolutely imperative to address the high computational cost ensuing from a segmentation task for a larger image. To make a breakthrough in reducing the computational cost, we will combine the proposed method with a well-known method: a patch-wise segmentation method.

To establish the superiority of the patch-wise segmentation over the usual segmentation without using patch images, we will demonstrate that the former completes a given segmentation task much faster. We create a cross image with mild noise (e.g., Fig 3), repeat the segmentation 100 times, and record the average computational time of the 100 trials. Table 2 reports the results of the patch-wise segmentation with various patch sizes being tried.

Table 2: Computational times when patch images of various sizes are used.

L (length)	T (seconds)	N (# of patches)	T/N ($\times 10^{-5}$)
4	0.725	9,801	7.406
8	0.993	9,409	10.563
16	1.652	8,649	19.109
32	5.830	7,225	80.703
64	78.790	4,761	165.492
80	192.128	3,721	516.334
100	485.554	2,601	1,866.797

The first column (denoted by L) represents the length of the square patch used for the segmentation while the second column (denoted by T) reports the average computational time when the square patch of the corresponding length is used. The third column (denoted by N) represents the number of extracted patch images during the entire segmentation. Since a stride of 2 is used when a square patch slides both horizontally and vertically, N is equivalent to $[(200 - L)/2 + 1]^2$. Following the third column, the fourth column (denoted by T/N) reports the average time taken for segmentation of a single square patch where the figure in the parenthesis is a unit of computational time. It is plain beyond misapprehension that the computational time decreases dramatically as a patch of a smaller size is used. As reported in the table, using a 4×4 patch yields the least amount of computational time. Motivated by this fact, the patch-wise segmentation with the 4×4 patch will be used for the following analysis unless specified otherwise.

3.2 Image segmentation of simulated images

In this section, we will segment various simulated images (circle, square, triangle, and star) with

noise. To visualize the performance of the proposed method, we invert the colors of the resulting images after segmentation, i.e., transforming white pixels to black pixels or vice versa. Figures 2-5 show original images together with their segmented outputs: Figure 2 shows the result pertaining to the original image without any noise while Figures 3, 4, and 5 show the results when the original image is contaminated with mild, moderate, and severe noise, respectively.

Figure 2: Original images (top) and segmented images (bottom).

Figure 3: Original images with mild noise (top) and segmented images (bottom).

Figure 4: Original images with moderate noise (top) and segmented images (bottom).

Several points are worth mentioning here. First, the proposed method returns perfectly-segmented images when there is no noise (Figure 2) or exists mild noise (Figure 3). Even in the presence of moderate noise, the proposed method shows very good segmentation performance; there are only a few false-positively segmented (FPS) pixels that are wrongly segmented as white pixels. Note that the number of FPS pixels in the final segmented image increases when images contain severe noise as shown in Figure 5. Second, it is clear to see the border lines between S_1^\dagger (white) and S_2^\dagger (black) get blurred as the noise gets stronger and poses a serious impediment to accurate segmentation. A closer look at the images with the severe noise reveals that the border lines of the segmented images are not straight but all saw-edged. In an effort to reduce (or remove completely if possible) those FPS pixels, we integrate the patch-wise segmentation with another well-celebrated digital filtering technique: median filtering. The median filtering has been popular and widely used in digital image processing for its several merits: see, e.g., Huang (1979) for more details. Figure 6 shows the results of the patch-wise segmentation with or without the median filtering. As shown in the figure, it is crystal-clear that there is a stark difference between the two figures: most of the FPS pixels are

Figure 5: Original images with severe noise (top) and segmented images (bottom).

removed when the median filtering is applied. Thus, the median filtering will be also used together with the proposed method unless otherwise noted.

Figure 6: Segmented image without (left) and with (right) the median filtering.

3.3 Real examples

The previous section observed that the performance of the proposed method comes as an amazement. However, the results obtained from the simulated images in the previous section should be treated and interpreted with considerable caution. It is not surprising to frequently observe that the excellence of methods with the simulated data is belied by the poor performance in real data: they start brilliantly with the simulated data but sink into or below mediocrity with real data. At this juncture, we have to answer the following question: can the proposed method replicate the theoretical result obtained so far when it is applied to the real data? Successful replication will lend credence to the proposed method, while failure to do that will cast a pall of suspicion over the method. In view of this, showing good performance for real data is crucial. To this end, this section; (1) assesses the performance of the proposed method when the real data is used for segmentation; and (2) demonstrates that the proposed method will remain competitive even when it is adopted for handling real data, thereby consolidating its position as the potential option for the image segmentation.

3.3.1 Radiology image data

Computed Tomography (CT) imaging is a cornerstone of radiology, particularly in evaluating traumatic injuries. It produces tomographic slices reconstructed from multiple projection images, offering crucial clinical information such as the diagnosis of acute intracranial hemorrhages and fractures. However, CT uses ionizing radiation to generate images, which necessitates efforts in modern radiologic practice to minimize radiation exposure for patient safety: see, e.g., Brenner and Hall (2007), McCollough and Rajiah (2023), and Schweitzer et al. (2019). This creates a challenge: as radiation exposure decreases, image noise increases, thereby complicating the application of conventional segmentation algorithms to lower-quality images.

Acute hemorrhages in the brain and other areas generally have higher attenuation (or higher value on CT images), which is a distinctive finding for the detection of hemorrhages. Intracranial hemorrhages require fast and accurate diagnosis, and measurement of the degree of the hemorrhages has great value in a clinical context. In this example, we applied the proposed method to segment hemorrhagic lesions in the brain.

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a debilitating demyelinating disease of the central nervous system, affecting the brain and spinal cord: see Reich et al. (2018) for more details. It causes tissue damage in the brain, and detecting these lesions and their patterns is vital for diagnosis and disease monitoring. Magnetic resonance (MR) imaging is particularly well-suited for this task due to its excellent soft-tissue contrast. However, the choice of MR imaging sequences and parameters significantly impacts diagnostic accuracy. For MS lesion detection, Fluid-attenuated inversion recovery (FLAIR) imaging – that is special kind of the MR imaging – is commonly used because it provides strong contrast, highlighting hyperintense lesions against surrounding brain tissue: see Bakshi et al. (2001). Nonetheless, some lesions have indistinct margins, making segmentation a labor-intensive and challenging process.

3.3.2 Application of the proposed method to the real data

To numerically gauge the performance of the proposed method and demonstrate its superiority, we employ the Dice similarity coefficient (DSC). For given two images A and B , the DSC is defined as

$$DSC = \frac{2|A \cap B|}{|A| + |B|},$$

where $|\cdot|$ denotes the number of pixels in an image, while the intersection of two images denotes the common, overlapped image between them. The DSC value ranges from 0 to 1, indicating no and complete overlaps, respectively. In the following segmentation of real radiology images, the DSC will measure the concordance between images of lesions labeled by physicians and segmented by the proposed method: see, e.g., the second and third subfigures in Figures 7–10.

For the real data, we use the clinical MR and CT images of patients who have MS. In these images, the lesions are denoted by bright colors while normal cells are denoted by dark colors. In the gray-scale MR images, lesions have a pixel value of or close to 1 (representing white), while normal cells and background have a pixel value of or close to 0 (representing black). Figures 7–9 and Figure 10 report the results of the application of the proposed method to MR and CT images, respectively. In the sequel, each figure contains four subfigures; (1) axial or sagittal brain scan; (2) image of the lesions labeled by physicians; (3) image of the lesions segmented by the proposed method; and (4) the third image (highlighted by blue) that is superimposed on the first image. Observe that the DSC value in all following figures will be computed by using (2) and (3).

Figure 7: Axial MR scan image and segmentation result of the first patient.

Figure 7 reports an axial FLAIR image of the first MS patient where irregularly shaped hyperintense lesions are visible around the ventricles (dark structures in the central region). The distribution and shape of lesions shown in Figure 7 are typical in MS. The proposed method effectively segments most lesions with high clarity, and hence, yields a DSC value of 64.6%.

The axial FLAIR image of the second patient, reported in Figure 8, again shows the typical characteristic of MS lesions (irregularly-shaped hyperintensity). As in the case of the first patient, the proposed method effectively captures most lesions with precision and reports a similar DSC value (64.68%). It is worth noting that the proposed method, however, misspecified the small ventricles (surrounded lesions in the first image) as lesions and small lesions (near the larger ventricles in the first image) as normal brain tissues, thereby exacerbating the performance of the proposed method.

Unlike the previous two figures, Figure 9 reports a sagittal MR image of the third patient: an irregularly shaped MS lesion is observed along the left parieto-temporal periventricular white matter. Like the former cases, the proposed method displays a similar but more improved performance, that

Figure 8: Axial MR scan image and segmentation result of the second patient.

Figure 9: Sagittal MR scan image and segmentation result of the third patient.

is, higher concordance with physician-drawn labels, thereby showing a larger DSC value (73.74%). Some importance can be accorded to the result of Figure 9 in that it serves to illustrate the proposed method shows good prospects for being an alternative method of segmenting clinical images.

Figure 10: An image of brain tumors (a), the labeled image of brain tumors(b), the segmented image by the proposed method(c), the superimposed overlaid image(d), 64.56% DSC.

Figure 10 reports an axial CT image of the last patient with acute intracranial hemorrhage: two hyperdense hemorrhagic foci are observed in the right temporal lobe and insula, as well as in the posterior midline. The proposed method successfully segments these hemorrhagic lesions and demonstrates high concordance with the physician-drawn label with a DSC value of 61.2%. Notably, the method achieves precise contouring of hemorrhagic lesions despite the input data with a large amount of statistical noise.

From the above examples, the DSC ranges from 61% to 74%, demonstrating that our approach achieves accurate segmentation for both MRI and CT modalities. These results affirm the capability of the proposed method to effectively handle different types of images in radiology.

Of particular interest is the finding that the accuracy of segmentation, as measured by the DSC, is influenced by the complexity of lesions. Compared with cases with multiple lesions, cases with a single lesion yield higher DSC values. For instance, the proposed method achieves the highest DSC value (74%) when applied to the case of the third patient featuring a single, clearly defined lesion in the brain. In stark contrast to the previous case, the case of the first patient – where the MR scan image contains multiple lesions, which renders the segmentation task more challenging – shows a smaller DSC value (65%).

This disparity between the first and third cases highlights an important characteristic of the proposed method: it excels in scenarios where lesions are well-defined and isolated, while the existence of numerous lesions will mount more challenges of accurate segmentation, aggravate the performance of the proposed method, and finally result in a lower DSC value. However, it is also worth noting that the proposed method demonstrates robust segmentation capabilities by achieving a decent DSC value of 65% even in the complex case.

4. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the MD estimation methodology is versatile in that it can be applied to image segmentation, thereby extending its domain of application from traditional statistical problems to applied problems. This paper confines the investigation to the case of $K = 2$ only, i.e., there exist two regions (S_1^\dagger and S_2^\dagger) to segment. Investigation of the case of $K \geq 3$ will be an extension of the findings in this study and form future research. The findings in Section underscore the potential effectiveness of the proposed method for real clinical segmentation tasks, whereas its limitation becomes evident in dealing with complex images, which should be addressed in future research.

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